

A New High Impact Resin System for Advanced Composites with 300°F (150°C) Properties

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ABSTRACT

A new high impact resin system has been developed which shows great promise in the field of advanced composites. This matrix resin offers features such as easy processability (low flow characteristics), high level of performance at 130-150°C (wet), no reaction volatiles, high impact resistance, excellent solvent resistance, and good out time properties. The resin system reacts via an addition type polymerization and is cured at 180°C. When combined with the new high strain carbon fibers, this resin can offer significant improvements and new applications in the area of advanced composites.

INTRODUCTION

Heretofore, high impact matrix resins used in the aerospace industry were limited to temperature usage of 130-150°C. These systems are epoxy based and usually use either an aromatic amine or dicyandiamide as the curing agent. The toughening component is generally a CTBN type elastomer. Other widely used aerospace resins such as Narmco 5208, have become base line systems for commercial aircraft and other aerospace applications. These types of materials generally use epoxy novolacs and/or nitrogen containing epoxies (TGMDA) in the resin matrix and are cured with diaminodiphenyl sulfone. A major drawback of these systems is that they are inherently brittle. Both the above types of systems will be used in advanced composites for secondary structures in production aircraft through at least the mid-1980's.

A long sought goal has been to develop a resin system that combines the attributes of both of the above systems and is characterized by excellent impact resistance (toughness), improved processability and hot wet strength retention at 130-150°C. When developed, such a system could be introduced in advanced composites for primary structure aircraft applications in the mid-1980's.

DISCUSSION

Toughness, as a composite requirement, has only recently been given more than cursory consideration. Impact damage resistant structures from carbon fiber reinforced composite materials have been slow in development primarily because of lack of a market viable high strain fiber. With the recent availability of approximately 210 million kPa modulus fibers with strain capabilities up to 2%, significant toughness (damage resistance) in advanced composites has become feasible.

Although some impact resistance improvements in composites are demonstrated using standard laminating resins, full translation of fiber properties, in terms of both developed strengths and toughness could not be accomplished with existing resin systems.

Narmco set out to develop a set of matrix resins, which, in combination with high strain carbon fiber, would yield ultimate performance properties from these reinforcements. Our goal was to provide materials which could be processed like an epoxy, but would demonstrate superior hot-wet strength retention, impart excellent impact resistance and develop full translation of fiber properties in composite form.

Preliminary Screening Methods

At Narmco, we employ a modified Gardner Impact Test for screening purposes in evaluations of relative toughness (impact resistance) of experimental formulations. We use 3K-70P carbon fabric (standard Celion) as reinforcement in a five ply layup. We measure the depth and area of damage which results from four separate levels of impact loading. Using these results and an equation developed in-house, we generate a numerical value we refer to as the damaged area function. The larger the number, the more brittle and impact sensitive is the composite.

Short beam shear strengths are obtained from similarly reinforced (3K-70P fabric) 12 ply laminates. Referring to Figure 1, it can be seen that epoxy materials fall into two general classes; first, high temperature (approximately 150°C) performing brittle materials, such as Narmco's 5208, and secondly, somewhat tougher moderate temperature (approximately 100°C) systems, such as Narmco's 5240/5241. The shaded areas generally encompass the ranges found for these types of materials.

At the outset of our development, we recognized the probable requirement for developing a system other than epoxies for our primary thrust. Figure 1 graphically describes our success in achieving the goals. Narmco believes the low impact sensitivity of the new resins coupled with very good hot (wet) short beam shear strengths, at least equaling 5208, represents a significant advance in laminating resin technology.

Composite Results

Some composite data representative of these materials are presented in the following tables. Table I outlines unidirectional laminate data which was obtained from high strain (1.8%) carbon fiber and Narmco's 5245 resin. The controlled flow prepreg was prepared at $34 \pm 2\%$ resin content at an areal fiber weight of 145 ± 2 g/m². The cure cycle was a straight heat-up to 184°C at 2°C/minute under 65 kPa, followed by three hours at 184°C and a standard slow cool down under pressure. The vacuum bag was vented to the atmosphere after application of pressure at room temperature prior to heat-up.

Table II displays woven fabric short beam shear strengths developed from 3K-70P, 1.4% strain fiber reinforcement along with aircraft fluids exposure data. Table III presents a comparison of this newly formulated resin system (5245) with two currently used systems; 5208 (brittle, but excellent 130-150°C mechanical property values), and 5241 (medium impact and good 100°C mechanical property values). This latter data is based on unidirectional laminates (normal strain fiber) cured by Narmco's recommended cure cycles.

The P_f (instrumented impact) entry in Tables I and III is the maximum (peak) load absorbed during a low velocity impact on a 12 ply quasi-isotropic laminate. The relative values in Table III are at least good qualitative measures of the relative toughness of the three resin systems while the effect of fiber strain capability is reflected in comparison of the P_f value of Table III (1.4% strain) and Table I (1.8% strain); 204.6N versus 366.6N. The P_i (failure initiation load) is found at about 310N in Figure 2; which is the trace developed with the ECI Dynatup instrument during test of high strain carbon fiber (1.8%)/5245 material.

Table IV lists the results developed using a Narmco 5245/(1.8% strain fiber) prepreg. These results include some new tests which are intended to establish a survivability level for impact damaged composites.

The open hole tension and compression test results are derived from an eight ply (0/± 45/90) and sixteen ply (0/± 45/90₂/± 45/0)_S layup respectively. A 3.7 x 30 cm. specimen is machined with a .62 cm. diameter hole machined in the geometric center of the laminate. The compression load and strain after impact values result from end-on compression testing of a 10 x 15 cm. laminate with a 36 ply quasi-isotropic ply orientation. The initial and residual values are obtained after impact with 0, 13.3 and 22.2 joules loadings per cm. of laminate thickness.

Resin Rheology

Figure 3 is a behavioral profile developed from 5245 resin at a constant 2°C/minute heat-up rate. The "minimum" in the viscosity curve occurs at about 95°C and represents that point where several factors interact to bring about early reversal in the normal viscosity/temperature curve found in simple epoxy systems such as 5208. The most important of these factors in our formulations include: 1) "extension" of dissolved high polymer materials; 2) particular reaction rate accelerations, and 3) interactions between resin and inorganic fillers changes, all as a consequence of elevated temperature and resin advancement levels.

The low flow properties of the 5245 resin are developed through a combination of appropriate resin chemistry adjustments and use of carefully selected additives. These devices naturally affect the ultimate properties of the cured resin and hence the composite properties.

Trade-offs between the resin producibility, prepreg preparability, fabricability, cure profile requirements and ultimate property values must be continually recognized.

CONCLUSIONS

The emergence of new high strain carbon fiber coupled with the development of the newly formulated Narmco 5245 resin system(s) opens the door for damage resistant ultra high performance materials

suitable for use as primary load bearing structure in today's subsonic aircraft.

BIOGRAPHIES

Lawrence C. Hopper is currently Manager of New Product and Process Development, Narmco Materials, Inc., a subsidiary of Celanese Corporation.

Edward S. Harrison joined the staff in Narmco's R&D department last April. One of his main areas of responsibility is in the matrix resin field. He joins Narmco after five years at General Dynamics/Convair Division and fifteen years with Whittaker R&D Division.

Steve G. Kim has been with Narmco over three years as a Product Development Chemist in the R&D group. His experience includes employment with DuPont and Sohio in similar positions. His primary area of interest is matrix resin development.

Kenneth A. Lowe is Product Development Chemist. He has been with Narmco in the R&D group for 13 years. Four years at U.S. Polymeric preceded his Narmco employment. His major interests include resin formulation and application of computer technologies to R&D and divisional operations.

Figure 1

○ - Dry ● - Wet

Total Energy - 25.1 Ft.-Lbs. Load, Max. - 824.2 Lbs.
 Impact Velocity - 7.13 Ft./Sec. Zero Load - 21.5 Ft.-Lbs. Total

Figure 2 - Instrumented Impact Test

Figure 3 - Behavioral Profile of Narmco 5245 Resin
 (2°C/minute 50-160°C)

TABLE I

RIGIDITE 5245/HIGH STRAIN CARBON FIBER (1.8%)
UNI-TAPE, 34 ± 2% RESIN CONTENT, A.F.W. 145 ± 4 g/m²

R.T. Tensile Strength*	2,410 MPa	350,000 psi
R.T. Tensile Strain	16,000 μ ε	16,000 μ ε
R.T. Compression*	1,520 MPa	220,000 psi
93°C Compression*	1,380 MPa	200,000 psi
93°C Compression (Wet)*	1,310 MPa	190,000 psi
R.T. Short Beam Shear	110 MPa	16,000 psi
93°C Short Beam Shear	93.1 MPa	13,500 psi
133°C Short Beam Shear	86.2 MPa	12,500 psi
93°C Short Beam Shear (Wet)**	79.3 MPa	11,500 psi
133°C Short Beam Shear (Wet)**	65.5 MPa	9,500 psi
P _F (Instrumented Impact)	367 N	824 lbs.

*Normalized to 62% Fiber Volume

**40 Hour Water Boil

TABLE II

RIGIDITE 5245/C-3000 (NORMAL STRAIN FIBER, (1.4%))
WOVEN 3K-70 P FABRIC, 38 ± 2% RESIN CONTENT

Short Beam Shear

R.T.	86.2 MPa	12,500 psi
93°C	77.2 MPa	11,200 psi
133°C	68.3 MPa	9,900 psi
149°C	51.7 MPa	7,500 psi
R.T. (Wet)	82.7 MPa	12,000 psi
93°C (Wet)	69.6 MPa	10,100 psi
133°C (Wet)	59.3 MPa	8,600 psi
149°C (Wet)	34.5 MPa	5,000 psi

TABLE III
UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBER LAMINATE PROPERTIES
 (Normal Strain Fiber - 1.4%)

<u>Tensile Strength</u>	<u>Matrix Resin</u>		
	<u>5245</u>	<u>5208</u>	<u>5241</u>
R.T.	1,720 MPa 250,000 psi	1,550 MPa 225,000 psi	1,650 MPa 240,000 psi
93°C	1,510 MPa 220,000 psi	1,510 MPa 220,000 psi	1,340 MPa 195,000 psi
133°C	1,480 MPa 215,000 psi	1,500 MPa 217,000 psi	1,140 MPa 165,000 psi
<u>Compression</u>			
R.T.	1,650 MPa 240,000 psi	1,430 MPa 207,000 psi	1,380 MPa 200,000 psi
93°C	1,510 MPa 220,000 psi	1,340 MPa 195,000 psi	1,210 MPa 175,000 psi
93°C (Wet)	1,450 MPa 210,000 psi	1,210 MPa 175,000 psi	1,030 MPa 150,000 psi
133°C	1,210 MPa 175,000 psi	1,170 MPa 170,000 psi	-
133°C (Wet)	1,140 MPa 165,000 psi	965 MPa 140,000 psi	-
<u>Short Beam Shear</u>			
R.T.	110 MPa 16,000 psi	124 MPa 18,000 psi	110 MPa 16,000 psi
93°C	103 MPa 15,000 psi	103 MPa 15,000 psi	90 MPa 13,000 psi
93°C (Wet)	83 MPa 12,000 psi	90 MPa 13,000 psi	62 MPa 9,000 psi
133°C	90 MPa 13,000 psi	83 MPa 12,000 psi	41 MPa 6,000 psi
133°C (Wet)	62 MPa 9,000 psi	55 MPa 8,000 psi	-
<u>Impact</u>			
P _F (Instrumented Impact)	205 N 460 lbs.	56 N 125 lbs.	107 N 240 lbs.

TABLE IV

NARMCO 5245/CARBON FIBER (HIGH STRAIN 1.8%)

Tensile Properties (Uni)		
Strength	2,520 MPa	366 ksi
Strain RT	17,160 $\mu\epsilon$	
Modulus	147 GPa	21.3 Msi
Strength	2,620 MPa	380 ksi
Strain (-73°C) (-100°F)	15,770 $\mu\epsilon$	
Modulus	1680 GPa	24.4 Msi
Compression Strength		
RT	1,320 MPa	192 ksi
93°C (200°F)	1,210 MPa	175 ksi
93°C (200°F) Wet*	1,180 MPa	171 ksi
Open Hole Tensile Strength		
RT	470 MPa	68.1 ksi
-73°C (-100°F)	435 MPa	63.1 ksi
Open Hole Compression Strength		
RT	335 MPa	48.6 ksi
93°C (200°F)	292 MPa	42.3 ksi
Compression Strength After Impact		
0	354 MPa	51,300 ksi
13.3 Joule/cm. (300 In.Lbs./In. of thickness)	405 MPa	58,800 ksi
22.2 Joule/cm. (500 In.Lbs./In. of thickness)	273 MPa	39,600 ksi
Compression Strain After Impact ($\mu\epsilon$)		
0	11,710	
13.3 Joule/cm. (300 In.Lbs./In. of thickness)	12,810	
22.2 Joule/cm. (500 In.Lbs./In. of thickness)	8,170	
*14 day soak in 71°C (160°F) water		